

Do job training and work environment affect the performance of weavers?

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Abstract

This study purpose to determine the effect of job training and work environment on the performance of Uis Karo weavers in Merek sub-district, Karo Regency. This study uses descriptive quantitative research methods. The population in this study was Uis Karo weavers in Merek sub-district, Karo Regency, using saturated sampling techniques and obtained a sample of 39 people. Data analysis techniques used the classical assumption test, multiple linear regression analysis, t-test, f-test, and coefficient of determination. The results showed that partially, the Job Training and Work Environment variables each had a significant effect on the performance of weavers with a significance value of 0.049 and 0,000. The simultaneous test shows that the Job Training and Work Environment variables have a significant influence on the performance of Uis Karo weavers in the Merek sub-district, Karo Regency with a significance value below 0.05, which is 0,000. The value of the coefficient of determination is 0.773, meaning that the contribution of the variable Job Training and Work Environment affects the Performance variable of 77.3%, while the remaining 22.7% is another independent variable which is not examined in this study such as the wage system, leadership and work discipline. Based on the research findings, it was concluded that the variable Job Training and Work Environment simultaneously affected the Weaver's Performance.

Keywords: Job Training, Work Environment and Performance, Weavers.

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INTRODUCTION

An organization or company is formed to achieve a particular purpose. The company will easily achieve the set goals if all existing resources have been working according to its function. The high level of awareness and responsibility for the burden of work will create a performance by employees. Human resources have the limits of their ability or performance, or sometimes often the deterioration of the quality of the human resources itself due to the number of serious challenges they will face when they are less prepared or lack of training in problem-solving. Therefore, the management of human resources by management must get the top priority. Hendri Rosa (2015), these test results show that job training influences employee performance. It means job training variable is one of the important things in improving employee performance. If the company conducts job training to employees, it will affect the performance of employees. Furthermore, Christopher Mathews (2015), states that the work environment has a positive impact on employee performance. That means if the work environment created by the company is adequate, it will improve the performance of employees. Performance is a function of the motivation and ability to accomplish a task or work one should have a degree of willingness and a certain level of ability. Performance is also an important factor in determining the success of a company or organization. When a company or organization has a well-performing human resource, it will be easier to achieve the goals of the company or organization. If employee performance decreases, it can cause the company's productivity to decline. David Harly Weol (2015), in his research, shows that workplace training and working environment have an effect on employee performance. Research shows the condition of the working environment and training on employee needs. The production of Uis in Merek subdistrict, Karo regency has been slight and decreasing every year. This is due to the decrease in performance of Uis Karo weaver. The decreasing performance of Uis Karo weavers can be caused by several factors, including the lack of training provided and inadequate work environment.

Table 1: The Production Level of Uis Karo Binaan Trias Tambun in Subdistrict of Merek, Karo Regency Period 2015-2016

No	Description	The year 2015		Percentage of realization in 2015	The year 2016		Percentage of realization in 2016
		Target	Realization		Target	Realization	
1.	Uis Nipes	1700	1370	80,6 %	1800	1360	75,55 %
2.	Uis Beka Buluh	1600	1280	80 %	1700	1260	74,12%
3.	Uis gara	1500	1110	74 %	1600	1088	68%
4.	Uis Jongkit	1200	790	65,83 %	1300	768	59,1%
	Total	5878	4550	75,83%	6400	4476	69,94%

The table above presents the realization of weaving production from 2015 to 2016, often the targets set by the organization are not achieved, even decreasing in 2015 the percentage of fabrication production weights of 75.83%, whereas in 2016 the percentage of realization of weaving production decreased by 69.94%. This is due to the decreasing performance of employees and they are unable to achieve the target. The current problem found by Uis Karo weaver in the subdistrict of Merek, Karo regency is the implementation of a job training as it is not as easy as imagined by many procedures to be carried out to produce the weavers

according to what SMEs want. Problems that often arise from job training are quite a lot of time in brief. Because time is very short, the weavers are less familiar with the right weave and how to produce the quality Uis Karo according to market demand. The work environment problem found by weavers in subdistrict of Merek, Karo Regency is that lack of light in the weaver's room, the size of the place for weaving is also quite narrow. Workspace conditions should be noted, comfort is much needed by Uis Karo. If the room and lighting conditions are poor, it can interfere with or inhibit the performance of weavers. Therefore, business owners must pay attention to the working environment, especially conditions and lighting in the workplace to improve the performance of weavers. Based on the above description, it is important for the authors to further examine the effect of job training and work environment on improving the performance of weavers.

Research Question

Based on the illustration described above, the problems that can be summarized in this study are as follows:

RQ1: Does job training affect the performance of Uis Karo weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency?

RQ2: Does the working environment affect the performance of Uis Karo weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency?

RQ3: Do job training and work environment affect the performance of Uis Karo weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Training

Fajar (2013) notes that job training is a learning process aimed at employees to make their work satisfactory. Dessler (2015) mentions that training is the process of teaching new or existing employees the basic skills they need to work on, it is concluded that the workforce or employee training for a company is a very important activity, where this can affect the level of productivity and work performance for employees and organizations or companies where they work.

Work Environment

Sunyoto (2013) explains that the working environment is everything around the worker and who influences themselves in the work they are responsible for. Sedarmayanti (2011) acknowledges that the working environment is all over the tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his method of work, and his working arrangements as an individual or as a group. Therefore, it can be stated that the working environment is a condition that affects employee performance in the workplace. Then, it can be understood that the working environment has a huge impact on the employees' habits of doing the job.

Performance

Hasibuan (2010) states that A work is accomplished by someone in performing the tasks assigned to him which is based on proficiency, experience and sincerity and timing. Mangkunegara (2011) reveals the performance term derived from the word job performance or actual performance. Therefore, the definition of performance is the result of quality work achieved by an employee in carrying out the work activity.

Hypotheses Development

H1; Job training has an influence on Uis Karo weaver performance in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency.

H2; The work environment has an influence on Uis Karo weaver performance in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency.

H3; Job training and work environment simultaneously have an influence on the performance of Uis Karo weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Job Training has a relation to the performance of the craftsmanship. It can be measured through job training indicators which are the materials needed in training in the form of special skills teaching and present the necessary knowledge, training instructor's ability as a source of information in identifying training needs. Methods are tailored to the type of training to be implemented, the objectives or the principles of learning to make the training process more effective, training participants are more important to take into account the type and type of workers to be trained, evaluating the training by taking into account the reaction rate and the final value of the training process.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative descriptive method. The purpose of the approach is to find out how significant relationships among variables are investigated, thus the conclusion will clarify the description of the object being investigated. Data collection in research uses primary data and secondary data. In this research the population is all Uis Karo Weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency is 39 people of weavers. Then, due to the small population size, the sampling techniques used are saturated sampling techniques that represent the technique of population. The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis after following the classic assumptions about normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity. Conclusions on hypotheses with t-test and F-tests at 5% significance level

RESULT

Multiple Linear Regression Tests

The multiple linear regression equation model as follows: $Y = 1,283 + 0,269X_1 + 0,667X_2$

On the equation, it can be seen that Job Training (X1) and Work Environment (X2) have a positive regression coefficient that proves its contribution to Performance (Y) Uis Karo Weaver in the subdistrict of Merek, Karo Regency. It shows that the increasing frequency of job training can improve performance. Likewise, with the working environment, with good and comfortable working environment conditions can also improve the performance of Weavers (Y) Uis Karo in the Subdistrict of Merek, Karo Regency.

T-Test

Testing is aimed to find out whether or not the significant influence of independent variables to the dependent variable partially. The results of a significant partial test can be summarized as follows The t-calculate Job Training variable (X1) is 2,036 higher than the t-table value by using the Microsoft Excel program, (TINV (0.05,36)), then the t-table value is 2,028 or sig t-value for Job training variables (0,049) lower than alpha (0,05). Thus, partial Job Training has a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo Weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency. The t-calculate Work Environment variable (X2) is 5,456 higher than the t-table value that is by using the Microsoft Excel program, (TINV (0.05,36)), then the t-table value is 2,028 or sig t-value for Work Environment variable (0,000) lower than alpha (0,05). Thus, Partially Work Environment has a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo Weaver in the sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency.

F-Test

F-test to see simultaneously the positive and significant effects of independent variables (X) on dependent variables (Y) by enabling significant values of F-test results. If the significance value of F-test is lower than ($<$) 0,05 then the independent variable (X) is simultaneously had a significant effect on the dependent variable (Y). While if the value of the significance produced on the F-test is higher than 0.05 then the independent variable (X) is stated to not affect the dependent variable (Y).

Determination Coefficient

The determination test (R²) aims to see how much the contribution of the independent variable in explaining the dependent variable. The value is 0-1, if the R Square value is closer to 1 then the model gets better. Based on the result of the research, the value of R Square determination coefficient 0,785 meaning 0,785% of performance variable can be influenced by Job Training and Work Environment variable, while the remaining 21,5% can be explained by other factors not studied in this research such as wage, leadership and work discipline.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Job Training on the Performance of Karo Weaver in Sub-district of Merek.

Partial hypothesis testing on job training variables affects weaver performance can be seen from significant job training value of 0.049 lower than the significance value of 0.05. Based on the t-test results, Job Training has a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo weaver in the Sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency. The result of this study is in line with the research of Sri Kurniawati Padma Dewi, Titi Laras. Efektif Jurnal Bisnis dan Ekonomi Vol.5 No.1 (2014) shows that Job training variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance

The Influence of Work Environment on Karo Weave Performance in the subdistrict of Merek

Partial hypothesis testing on working environment variables has an effect on weaver performance can be seen from significant work environment value of 0,000 lower than the significance value of 0.05. Based on the result of the t-test, the working environment has a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo weaver in Subdistrict of Merek, Karo Regency. The results of this study are in line with David Harly Weol's research. Jurnal Berkala Ilmiah Efisiensi Vol.15 No.05 (2015) shows that the working environment poses a positive effect

The Influence of Job Training and Work Environment on the Performance of Weavers Karo, Subdistrict of Merek.

Based on statistical F test, it can be seen that significant value of $0,000 < 0,05$, it is concluded that H1 is accepted means that Job training and work environment simultaneously have an effect on the performance of Uis Karo weaver in Sub-district of Karo Regency. This result is consistent with previous research results that are Hendri Rosa (2015) E-Jurnal Apresiasi Ekonomi Volume 3 Nomor 2 Mei 2015 shows that workplace training and working environment together affects the performance of weavers in Sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research, the conclusions that can be obtained by the researchers are (1) Partially, Job Training has a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo weaving in sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency where $t\text{-calculates } 2,036 > t\text{-tables of } 2,028$. (2) Partially, the work environment has a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo weaver in sub-district of Merek, Karo Regency where $t\text{-calculates } 5,456 > t\text{-tables of } 2,028$. (3) Simultaneously, job training and working environment have a significant effect on the performance of Uis Karo weaver in sub-district of Karo Regency where $F\text{-calculates is } 65,665 > F\text{-table of } 3,259$. Job training for a company can affect the level of productivity and work performance for employees and organizations. Working environment can affects employees performance in their workplace. It can be understood that the working environment has a huge impact on the employees' habits of doing the job. Performance is a result of quality work achieved by an employee in carrying out the work activity.

Suggestion

Based on the result of this research, the author gives the following suggestions; SMEs Trias Tambun in Sub-district Merek should provide periodical weaving training so that weavers have better skills and knowledge, so the performance of weavers can increase, as well as weavers can also produce high-quality weaving. SMEs Trias Tambun in Sub-district Merek should always look at the working environment for weavers, such as indoor lighting, facilities and machines to weave so weavers concentrate more on carrying out their work and achieving corporate goals. For the next researcher, the researcher expects that in the future, this research can be a reference as well as for research as it should add variables such as compensation, motivation and so forth which are related to performance, thereby adding literature studies and enriching scientific research.

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